

Spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum(VI) using salicylaldehyde 3-oxobutanoylhydrazone as a new analytical reagent

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Manuscript received 7 January 2005, revised 29 May 2006, accepted 6 June 2006

Abstract : Salicylaldehyde 3-oxobutanoylhydrazone (salicylaldehyde acetoacetic acid hydrazone, SAAH) has been used as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum(VI). The metal ion formed a 1 : 1 greenish-yellow complex with the reagent having absorption maximum at 405 nm, which was quantitatively extracted into benzene. Under the optimum conditions of the proposed procedure Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range of 0–18.7 $\mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method were found to be $9.96 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0096 \mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$ with a relative standard deviation of ± 0.0025 absorbance units and coefficient of variance as 0.25%, respectively. The proposed method has been applied successfully for micro determination of molybdenum in various alloy steels and a wide variety of synthetic and technical samples with satisfactory results.

Keywords : Molybdenum, hydrazone, spectrophotometry.

Many organic reagents including hydrazones^{1–5} and oximes^{6,7} are well known for their use in colorimetric methods but some of them have low sensitivities and suffer from many interferences⁸ and hence restrict their applicability to only a few samples of industrial importance. With a view to overcome this difficulty, we have used salicylaldehyde 3-oxobutanoylhydrazone (SAAH) as a new analytical reagent for molybdenum to develop a sensitive method for the colorimetric determination of molybdenum(VI) by extracting its complex into benzene from weakly hydrochloric acid medium.

Results and discussion

Under the experimental conditions of the proposed procedure the complex shows an absorption maximum at 405 nm. SAAH [0.2% (w/v) ethanolic solution] absorb strongly up to 320 nm and thereafter the absorbance decreased and becomes insignificant in the wavelength region around 405 nm. Therefore, all the absorbance measurements were carried out at 405 nm against the reagent blank prepared under identical conditions.

Extraction of the greenish-yellow complex was quantitative when acidity of the reaction medium was kept in the range 0.02–1.0 M with HCl. The absorbance of the complex when extracted from the solution of same acidity (0.5 M), adjusted with different acids, decreased in the order : HCl > CH₃COOH > H₂SO₄ ≈ HClO₄ > H₃PO₄. The effect of

variables on the absorbance of Mo^{VI}-SAAH complex was studied by keeping the concentration of molybdenum 1.04×10^{-5} M. The development of the maximum absorbance in benzene takes just 1 min and attained constancy thereafter up to 5 min equilibration time. 0.4–1.5 ml of ethanolic solution of SAAH (0.2% w/v) were sufficient to extract $\leq 18.7 \mu\text{g Mo}$ in a single extraction to give maximum and constant absorbance. Higher concentration of the reagent caused turbidity in the solvent phase. Therefore, the extractions were carried out using 1 ml of the reagent each time. The order of addition of water and acid to the Mo solution is not important in the procedure, provided the SAAH is added after the addition of the benzene and the contents are shaken immediately so that the complex is transferred to the solvent phase as soon as it is formed. If the reagent is added prior to the addition of the solvent and waited for some time before shaking, low absorbance is obtained which may be due to lower stability of the complex in aqueous phase.

The complex gets extracted into organic solvents : (absorbance in parentheses) benzene (0.519), carbon tetrachloride (0.505), chloroform (0.465), 1,2-dichloroethane (0.445), carbon disulphide (0.400), butyl acetate (0.380), isopentyl acetate (0.305), isobutyl methyl ketone (0.260), isopentyl alcohol (0.190) and ethyl acetate (0.135). A maximum absorbance was found in benzene. It was further con-

Table 1. Comparison of the proposed method with the existing methods

Sr. no.	Aqueous conditions	i) Solvent ii) λ_{\max}	i) Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) ii) Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$)	Beer's law range ($\mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-3}$)	Ref. no.
1.	Mo^{VI} , salicylaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone, EDTA, ascorbic acid, HClO_4	i) Isopentyl alcohol ii) 430 nm	i) 6.5×10^3 ii) 0.0148	0.4–12.0	1
2.	Mo^{VI} , di(methylethylketone)thiocarbohydrazone, ethanol- H_2O , pH 0.5–1.8	i) – ii) 380 nm	i) 6.6×10^3 ii) 0.0144	1.0–15.0	2
3.	Mo^{VI} , pH 2.6, gossypol isonicotinoylhydrazone	i) <i>n</i> -Butanol ii) –	i) 7.1×10^3 ii) 0.0135	0.1–7.0	3
4.	Mo^{VI} , ethanol, 2'-hydroxyacetophenone benzoylhydrazone, 0.5 M HCl	i) CCl_4 ii) 390 nm	i) 8.53×10^3 ii) 0.0112	0–14.5	4
5.	Mo^{VI} , 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone, 1.5 M HCl, ethanol	i) CHCl_3 ii) 470 nm	i) – ii) –	0.02–4.0	5
6.	Mo^{VI} , salicylaldoxime isoniazid, CH_3COOH	i) – ii) 430 nm	i) 3.6×10^3 ii) 0.026	1.0–19.0	6
7.	Mo^{VI} , resacetophenone oxime, 0.1 M HCl	i) 20% Cyclohexanol in C_6H_6 ii) 400 nm	i) 0.1×10^3 ii) 0.9594	100–500	7
8.	Mo^{VI} , salicylaldehyde 3-oxobutanoylhydrazone, 1 M HCl	i) Benzene ii) 405 nm	i) 9.96×10^3 ii) 0.0096	0–18.7	Proposed method

firmed by the complete absence of molybdenum in the raffinate as tested by the more sensitive thiocyanate-pyrogallol method⁹. Other solvents extract the complex partially, but the color intensity of the complex remains constant for more than 2 days in benzene. Single extraction with an equal volume (10 ml) of benzene was found to be sufficient for quantitative transfer of the complex. Hence, it was chosen for further studies.

Beer's law, standard deviation and sensitivity : The absorbance of the greenish-yellow complex in benzene showed a linear response up to $18.7 \mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$ and obeyed Beer's law in this range of Mo concentration, however, the practical range of accurate determination of molybdenum obtained from Ringbom's plot¹⁰ is $0.12\text{--}13.18 \mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$ at 405 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method were found to be $9.96 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0096 \mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The relative standard deviation of the method was found to be ± 0.0025 absorbance units with coefficient of variance as 0.25%.

Stoichiometry of the complex : The composition of the complex determined by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburg and Cooper¹¹ was found to be 1 : 1.

Effect of diverse ions : Under optimum conditions of the procedure, the effect of various anions, cations and complexing agents were studied. Tolerance limits for the determination of $50 \mu\text{g Mo}^{\text{VI}}$ were 45 mg each of phosphate, nitrate, sulphate, thiocyanate and ascorbic acid; 25 mg each of EDTA, acetate, thiourea and chloride; 20 mg borate; 10

mg fluoride; 2.1 mg each of tartrate and citrate; and 0.5 ml of glycerol. However, oxalate interfered seriously. All the anions were added well before the addition of the reagent as their sodium salts except thiocyanate, which was added as potassium salt.

Table 2. Analysis of samples by the proposed method

Sr. no.	Composition of sample Matrix ^a	Mo added (μg)	Mo found ^b (μg)
1.	[Fe (7.00), Cu (0.100), Ni (0.912), Cr (1.900)] ^c	100	100.0
2.	[Fe (0.03), Ni (1.89), Cr (0.6), Cu (0.195), W (0.06), Al (0.03), Mn (0.03)] ^c	150	150.7
3.	[Fe (1.72), Ni (0.448), Cr (0.60), Cu (0.032), Mn (0.060), Co (0.0028)] ^c	120	119.6
4.	[Fe (7.995), Ni (0.99), Cr (1.399), Mn (0.99)] ^c	45	45.2
5.	[Fe (4.62), W (1.19), Cr (0.7)] ^c	175	175.2
6.	BCS (219/4)	0.58% ^d	0.581%
7.	BCS (261/1)	0.11% ^d	0.101%
8.	BCS (406/1)	1.00% ^d	0.970%

^aNumber in brackets indicates mg amounts of elements in the aliquot for analysis.

^bAverage of triplicate analyses.

^cSample no. 1–5 are analogous to stainless-U, cristite, stainless steel, cast steel and steel CA-15, respectively.

^dCertified value.

Among the cations, the following have no effect on the determination of $50 \mu\text{g Mo}^{\text{VI}}$ under the optimum conditions of the procedure : 10 mg each of Mn^{II} , Zn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Mg^{II} , Co^{II} ,

Th^{IV}, U^{VI}, Ni^{II}, Ba^{II}, Ag^I, Ca^{II}, Se^{IV}, Hg^{II}, As^V and Sr^{II}; 5 mg each of Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, Cd^{II}; 0.2 mg each of Re^{VII}, Pt^{IV}, Rh^{III}; 0.1 mg each of Pb^{II} and Ru^{III}; 0.05 mg each of Os^{VIII} and Pd^{II}. Interferences due to 10 mg Fe^{III} and 5 mg of Cr^{VI} were prevented by adding 40 and 10 mg ascorbic acid, respectively. By the addition of 40 mg ascorbic acid and then 30 mg disodium EDTA interference due to 5 mg of V^V was eliminated. 10 mg Cu^{II} and 0.5 mg Ti^{IV} were masked with 10 mg and 2.5 mg disodium EDTA, respectively, whereas 5 mg of W^{VI} can be tolerated in presence of 10 mg sodium fluoride. The presence of 1 mg Bi^{III} has given precipitate in the procedure but the extraction was performed as such. Difficulty in the separation of two layers was caused due to hydrolysis of Sb^{III}. The absorbance decreased significantly in presence of Ce^{IV} and Zr^{IV} while Sn^{II} enhanced it due to the formation of an extractable colored species, and thus interfered seriously.

Applications : The proposed method can be compared with some of the existing methods¹⁻⁷ as regards its sensitivity and selectivity (Table 1). The metal ions which interfere seriously in other methods⁸, either do not interfere or the interference can be eliminated easily in the present procedure. The method takes only 10 min in a single determination and much less in series operations. Further, the synthesis of salicylaldehyde 3-oxobutanoylhydrazone is very simple and convenient. Thus the proposed method can be used for routine determination of molybdenum in the technical alloy steels and synthetic samples successfully (Table 2).

Experimental

An Elico SL 164 UV-Vis Double beam spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched cells was used for absorbance measurements. A stock solution of sodium molybdate dihydrate (Thomas Baker, A.R.) containing 1 mg Mo ml⁻¹ was prepared in deionised water and standardized by the oxine method¹². Working standards (10–100 µg Mo ml⁻¹ level) were obtained by suitable dilutions of the stock solution. Solutions of other diverse metal ions and anions of analytical importance were prepared in deionised water or dilute acids by dissolving their salts (A.R.) for interference studies.

Salicylaldehyde 3-oxobutanolhydrazone (SAAH) was prepared by literature method¹³ and dissolved in ethanol to give 0.2% (w/v) solution.

Preparation of salicylaldehyde acetoacetic acid hydrazone : Salicylaldehyde acetoacetic acid hydrazone was prepared by taking equimolar solutions of acetoacetic acid hydrazide and salicylaldehyde in aqueous ethanol. The contents were refluxed for 2 h and cooled to room tempera-

ture for separation of solid product. The solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from hot aqueous methanol solution, m.p. 220 °C, yield 80% and was dissolved in ethanol to give 0.2% (w/v) solution.

Synthetic and technical samples : Synthetic samples are prepared by mixing molybdenum solution with the solutions of other diverse metal ions of analytical importance in suitable proportions, as shown (Table 2).

A steel sample (0.1 g) is dissolved in 3 ml concentrated HCl and 1 ml concentrated HNO₃ by slow heating on a sand bath. The solution is evaporated to a thick mass and treated with 10 ml of 0.5 M HCl. It is then transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume is made upto the mark with the deionized water. To a 1 ml aliquot is added 50 mg ascorbic acid and Mo is determined by the proposed procedure.

Benzene (Qualigens, S.Q.) was distilled and the fraction distilling at 79.5–80 °C was used for extraction. Hydrochloric acid (1 M) was prepared by suitable dilution of 11 M HCl (Ranbaxy). All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Procedure : To an aliquot (1 ml) of the solution containing ≤18.7 µg Mo^{VI} and other metal ions in a 100 ml separatory funnel were added 0.5 ml of 1 M HCl and enough deionized water to make the volume of aqueous phase 9 ml. To this were added 10 ml of benzene followed by 1.0 ml of ethanolic solution of SAAH (0.2% w/v) and the contents were equilibrated for 1 min without any delay. The organic layer was passed through a pretreated Whatman filter paper (No. 41, 9 cm size) to remove water droplets and collected into a 10 ml measuring flask. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 405 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of metal ion was computed from the calibration curve prepared under identical conditions of the procedure.

Modification for Fe, Cr, V, Cu, Ti, Sn and W : Each of Fe^{III}, Cr^{VI}, V^V, Cu^{II}, Ti^{IV} and Sn^{II} when present in the samples were completely masked with ascorbic acid and/or disodium EDTA while W^{VI} was masked with sodium fluoride when added to the aqueous phase well before the addition of the solvent and reagent. The respective amount of masking agents used was mentioned under the effect of diverse ions. Otherwise, the procedure remains the same.

Acknowledgement

Our sincere thanks are due to the Principal, Guru Nanak Khalsa College, Yamuna Nagar, Haryana and the Principal, N. A. S. College, Meerut for providing laboratory facilities.

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